

Tri-*n*-butylstannyl chloride-sodium cyanoborohydride mediated regioselective reductive demethoxylation of alkyl methyl ketals

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A regioselective reductive demethoxylation of alkyl methyl ketals employing sodium cyanoborohydride in the presence of a catalytic amount of tri-*n*-butyltin chloride as Lewis acid is described.

The reductive cleavage of acetals and ketals to ethers is a synthetically useful transformation in organic synthesis¹. In this context, the dissociative nucleophilic substitution of acetals and ketals activated by a Lewis acid, has grown to become an important reaction in organic synthesis and thus studies regarding the choice of an appropriate Lewis acid to bring out the relevant transformation has been the subject of numerous investigations². The function of trialkyltin halide, in organic synthesis, as an electrophile is well recognised. During the last fifteen years, utility of tri-*n*-butyltin chloride (catalytic) in combination with sodium cyanoborohydride (stoichiometric) for the *in situ* generation of catalytic tri-*n*-butyltin hydride to carry out radical cyclisation reactions has also been well established³. However, to the best of our knowledge, there is no report on the use of trialkyltin halides as Lewis acids in synthetic transformations⁴. Recently, during our investigations on the development of a radical cyclisation based methodology for cyclopentannulation of allyl alcohols⁵, we have discovered⁶ that trialkyltin halide in the presence of sodium cyanoborohydride reductively demethoxylates a mixed ketal, e.g. **2**→**3** (eqn. 1), suggesting the role of tri-*n*-butyltin halide as a Lewis acid. In order to establish the use of tri-*n*-butyltin chloride and sodium cyanoborohydride for the selective cleavage of ketals, further investigations were undertaken⁷.

To begin with, the mixed ketal **4a** was chosen as the starting material, which was derived from cyclohexanone. Thus, reaction of cyclohexanone and trimethyl orthoformate in the presence of *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (PTSA) at 150° furnished the enol ether **5**⁸. Treatment of the enol ether **5**

with dodecanol in methylene chloride in the presence of a catalytic amount of pyridinium *p*-toluenesulfonate (PPTS) furnished the mixed ketal **4a**. Refluxing a solution of the mixed ketal **4a** in tertiary butyl alcohol with 0.15 equivalents of tri-*n*-butyltin chloride and an excess of sodium cyanoborohydride for nine hours furnished the ether **6a** containing trace amount of starting material, in 62% yield, whose structure was established from its spectral data. The molecular ion appeared at *m/z* 268 in the mass spectrum of **6a**. The ¹H NMR spectrum revealed the absence of methoxy group and the presence of resonances, a multiplet at δ 3.32–3.52 due to O-CH and O-CH₂, a multiplet at 1.00–2.00 due to methylenes and a distorted triplet at 0.88 ppm due to the terminal methyl group, establishing the structure of the ether **6a**. The ¹³C NMR spectrum exhibited a doublet at δ 77.4 due to O-CH and a triplet at 68.0 ppm due to O-CH₂ besides other expected signals, confirming the structure of the ether **6a**. The formation of the ether **6a** can be readily explained based on the well established ionic hydrogenation mechanism^{1a} (Scheme 1) wherein a Lewis acid (LA) complexes with one of the alkoxy groups of the ketal **7** leading to the cleavage of the alkoxy group and generation of the oxonium ion **8** which on reduction with hydride ion results in the formation of the ether **9**. It is apparent that in the present transformation tri-*n*-butyltin chloride is acting as a

Lewis acid. The selective cleavage of the methoxy group in preference to other alkoxy group may be due to the complexation of the tri-*n*-butyltin chloride with the less crowded methoxy group of the mixed ketal **4a**.

To test the generality, the reaction was carried out with

various ketals. Thus, the ketals 4b-l were prepared either directly from the corresponding ketones or via the appropriate enol ether and alcohols using the standard procedures. The ketal 2 was prepared by radical cyclisation of the bromoketal 1 using tri-*n*-butyltin hydride and azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN)⁵. Refluxing a solution of the ketals 2,

Scheme 1

4b-i in tertiary butyl alcohol with tri-*n*-butyltin chloride (0.15–1.0 equivalents) and 1.0–3.0 equivalents of sodium cyanoborohydride furnished the ethers⁹ 3, 6b-i in moderate to good yields and the results are summarised in Table 1. The salient features are as follows. In the case of mixed ketals 2, 4a,b,h,i demethoxylated products were obtained predominantly. Interestingly, even with the ethyl methyl ketal 4h, only small amount ($\approx 5\%$) of the deethoxylated product 6c could be observed, whereas the reaction of the diethyl ketal 4j was found to be very slow, even with 0.6 equivalents of tri-*n*-butyltin chloride for 14 hours only a 2 : 1 mixture of the unreacted starting material and the ether 6h was obtained. On refluxing a 1 : 1 mixture of the diethyl ketal 4j and dimethyl ketal 4c in tertiary butyl alcohol with 0.15 equivalents of tri-*n*-butyltin chloride and ≈ 2.0 equivalents of sodium cyanoborohydride furnished, predominantly, the demethoxylated product 6c from the dimethyl ketal 4c along with only small amount of the ethoxy ether 6h derived from the diethyl ketal 4j. No reductive cleavage was observed with cyclic ketals 4k and 4l even in the presence of a stoichiometric amount of tri-*n*-butyltin chloride. It is worth

Table 1

Entry	Ketal	Ether	Yield ^a
a	2	3	80
b	4b	6b	68
c	4c	6c	93
d	4d	6d	59
e	4e	6e	51
f	4f	6f	71
g	4g	6g	49
h	4h	6h	76
i	4j	6j	76
j	4l	6h	— ^b
k	4k	—	—
l	4l	—	—

^aYields refer to isolated and chromatographically pure products and are unoptimised ^bA 2 : 1 mixture of the starting material and the product

mentioning that the dimethyl acetals derived from araldehydes were found to be stable under these reaction conditions.

In conclusion, first synthetic application of trialkylhalostannane as a mild Lewis acid in reductive demethoxylation of ketals has been established, which in turn points to the limitation of the sodium cyanoborohydride and tri-*n*-butyltin

chloride combination for the *in situ* generation of tri-*n*-butyltin hydride in radical cyclisation reactions.

Experimental

General procedure for the preparation of ketals and acetals :

Method A : A solution of the ketone (1 g), trimethyl orthoformate (2 ml) and a catalytic amount of PTSA in methanol (5 ml) was refluxed for 4–6 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, treated with saturated aq. NaHCO₃ and extracted with ether (3 × 5 ml). The ether extract was washed with brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the solvent followed by rapid purification of the product through a small silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 40) as eluent furnished the dimethyl ketals.

Method B : A solution of a ketone (1 g), ethylene glycol (1.5 ml) and a catalytic amount of PTSA in dry benzene (20 ml) was refluxed with a Dean-Stark water trap for 6 h. Work-up and purification as described in method-A furnished the ethylene ketals.

Method C : A solution of an enol ether (1-methoxycyclohexene⁸ or α -methoxystyrene⁸ or 2-methoxypropene, 2 mmol), an alcohol (2 mmol) and a catalytic amount of PPTS in CH₂Cl₂ (5 ml) was magnetically stirred at room temperature for 12 h. Work-up and purification as described in method-A furnished the mixed ketals.

1-n-Dodecyloxy-1-methoxycyclohexane (4a) : Prepared in 85% yield from 1-methoxycyclohexene (5) and dodecanol employing method-C : ν_{\max} (neat) 1150, 1095, 1050, 925 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (90 MHz; CDCl₃) δ 3.36 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, O-CH₂), 3.20 (3H, s, O-CH₃), 1.20–1.80 (30H, m), 0.90 (3H, distorted t, terminal CH₃); *m/z* 267 (M-OCH₃, 16%), 131 (30), 113 (100), 99 (61), HRMS *m/z* for C₁₈H₃₅O (M-OCH₃), Calcd. : 267.2688. Found : 267.2695.

1-Methoxy-n-undecyloxycyclohexane (4b) : Prepared in 79% yield from 1-methoxycyclohexene and undecanol employing method-C : ν_{\max} (neat) 1165, 1110, 1060, 930 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (90 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 3.36 (2 H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, O-CH₂), 3.18 (3H, s, O-CH₃) 1.10–1.76 (28H, m), 0.90 (3H, distorted t, terminal CH₃); *m/z* 284 (M⁺, 3%), 253 (13), 131 (30), 113 (100), 99 (40), HRMS *m/z* for C₁₇H₃₃O (M-OCH₃), Calcd. : 253.2531. Found : 253.2538.

(1,1-Dimethoxyethyl)benzene (4c) : Prepared in 70% yield from acetophenone employing method-A : ν_{\max} (neat) 1370, 1275, 1200, 1145, 1100, 1085, 1040, 875, 765, 700 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (60 MHz; CCl₄) δ 7.20–7.80 (5H, m, ArH), 3.16 (6H, s, 2 × O-CH₃), 1.50 (3H, s, *tert*-CH₃).

4-Methyl-(1,1-dimethoxyethyl)benzene (4d) : Prepared

in 93% yield from 4-methylacetophenone employing the method-A : ν_{\max} (neat) 1600, 1500, 1360, 1275, 1180, 1145, 1100, 1040, 870, 820 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (90 MHz; CDCl₃) δ 7.13 and 7.38 (4H, AB q, *J* 8.0 Hz, ArH), 3.20 (6H, s, 2 × O-CH₃), 2.36 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 1.44 (3H, s, *tert*-CH₃); *m/z* 180 (M⁺, 2%), 165 (60), 150 (40), 149 (100), 119 (100), 91 (85), HRMS *m/z* for C₁₁H₁₆O₂, Calcd. : 180.1150. Found : 180.1094.

4-Methoxy-(1,1-dimethoxyethyl)benzene (4e) : Prepared in 85% yield from 4-methoxyacetophenone employing method-A : ν_{\max} (neat) 1610, 1510, 1370, 1310, 1280, 1250, 1175, 1150, 1110, 1040, 875, 835 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (90 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.86 and 7.42 (4H, AB q, *J* 8.5 Hz, ArH), 3.82 (3H, s, Ar-O-CH₃), 3.20 (6H, s, 2 × O-CH₃), 1.54 (3H, s, *tert*-CH₃).

4-Chloro-(1,1-dimethoxyethyl)benzene (4f) : Prepared in 92% yield from 4-chloroacetophenone employing method-A : ν_{\max} (neat) 1270, 1190, 1155, 1090, 1040, 1010, 880, 820 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (90 MHz; CDCl₃) δ 7.28 and 7.44 (4H, AB q, *J* 9.0 Hz, ArH), 3.16 (6H, s, 2 × O-CH₃), 1.52 (3H, s, *tert*-CH₃).

4-Bromo-(1,1-dimethoxyethyl)benzene (4g) : Prepared in 90% yield from 4-chloroacetophenone employing method-A : ν_{\max} (neat) 1585, 1390, 1370, 1265, 1190, 1145, 1110, 1095, 1040, 1010, 875, 825 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (90 MHz; CDCl₃) δ 7.34 and 7.48 (4H, AB q, *J* 8.6 Hz, ArH), 3.18 (6H, s, 2 × O-CH₃), 1.52 (3H, s, *tert*-CH₃); *m/z* 246 (M⁺ + 2, 5%), 244 (M⁺, 5%), 231 and 229 (70), 218 and 216 (50), 217 and 215 (100), 185 and 183 (40), 134 (40), 89 (100), HRMS *m/z* for C₉H₁₀BrO₂ (M-CH₃), Calcd. : 228.9864. Found : 228.9835.

(1-Ethoxy-1-methoxyethyl)benzene (4h) : Prepared in 83% yield from α -methoxystyrene and ethanol employing the method-C : ν_{\max} (neat) 1270, 1160, 1110, 1045, 955, 765, 700 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (60 MHz; CCl₄) δ 7.00–7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 3.35 (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz, O-CH₂), 3.15 (3H, s, O-CH₃), 1.47 (3H, s, *tert*-CH₃), 1.17 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 HZ, O-CH₂CH₃).

n-Dodecyl 2-methoxyprop-2-yl ether (4i) : Prepared in 61% yield from 2-methoxypropene and dodecanol employing method-C : ν_{\max} (neat) 1380, 1370, 1210, 1180, 1150, 1070, 1050, 845 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (90 MHz; CDCl₃) δ 3.38 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, O-CH₂), 3.20 (3H, s, O-CH₃), 1.36 (6H, s, CH₃-C-CH₃), 1.00–2.00 (20H, br s), 0.88 (3H, distorted t, terminal CH₃); *m/z* 227 (M-OCH₃, 1%), 140 (17), 111 (30), 98 (30), 97 (57), 55 (100).

(1,1-Diethoxyethyl)benzene (4j) : Prepared in 80% yield from acetophenone, triethyl orthoformate and ethanol em-

ploying method-A : ν_{\max} (neat) 1500, 1380, 1270, 1170, 1125, 1050, 955, 860, 765, 700 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (60 MHz; CCl_4) δ 7.15–7.65 (5H, m, ArH), 3.34 (4H, q, J 7.1 Hz, $2 \times \text{O-CH}_2$), 1.51 (3H, s, *tert*- CH_3), 1.20 (6H, t, J 7.1 Hz, $2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$).

2-Methyl-2-(4-methylphenyl)-1,3-dioxalane (4k) : Prepared in 94% yield from 4-methylacetophenone employing method-B : ν_{\max} (neat) 1365, 1245, 1190, 1095, 1035, 865, 815 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (90 MHz; CDCl_3) δ 7.12 and 7.38 (4H, AB q, J 8.0 Hz, ArH), 3.50–4.25 (4H, m, $\text{O-CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 2.35 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3), 1.66 (3H, s, *tert*- CH_3).

1,4-Dioxaspiro[4 5]decane (4l) : Prepared in 92% yield from cyclohexanone employing method-B : ν_{\max} (neat) 1450, 1365, 1280, 1160, 1105, 1040, 930 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (90 MHz; CDCl_3) δ 3.94 (4H, s, $\text{O-CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 1.20–2.40 (10H, m).

General procedure for reductive cleavage of ketals : To a magnetically stirred solution of the ketal (1 mmol) and $^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ (0.03 ml, 0.11 mmol) in dry *tert*-butyl alcohol (5 ml), was added NaCNBH_3 (100 mg, 1.59 mmol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed. After the completion of the reaction (monitored by TLC) the mixture was diluted with ether (10 ml), washed with 1% aq. ammonia and brine, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent and purification of the product on a silica gel column using hexane as eluent furnished the product.

Cyclohexyl n-dodecyl ether (6a) : Reductive cleavage of the ketal **4a** (150 mg, 0.5 mmol) with NaCNBH_3 (60 mg, 0.95 mmol) and $^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ (0.02 ml, 0.074 mmol) for 9 h furnished the ether **6a** (83 mg, 62%) as an oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 1360, 1110 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (90 MHz; CDCl_3) δ 3.32–3.52 (1H, m, O-CH), 3.42 (2H, t, J 7.0 Hz, O-CH_2), 1.00–2.00 (30H, m), 0.88 (3H, distorted t, terminal CH_3); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (22.5 MHz; CDCl_3) δ 77.4 (d, O-CH), 68.0 (t, O- CH_2), 32.4 (2C, t), 31.9 (t), 30.2 (t), 29.6 (5C, t), 29.4 (t), 26.2 (t), 25.9 (t), 24.3 (2C, t), 22.7 (t), 14.0 (q, terminal CH_3); m/z 268 (M^+ , 8%), 100 (26), 98 (24), 83 (100, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}^+$), HRMS m/z for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}$, Calcd. : 268.2766. Found : 268.2752.

Cyclohexyl n-undecyl ether (6b) : Reductive cleavage of the ketal **4b** (142 mg, 0.5 mmol) with NaCNBH_3 (60 mg, 0.95 mmol) and $^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ (0.02 ml, 0.074 mmol) for 9 h furnished the ether **6b** (87 mg, 68%) as an oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 1360, 1110 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (90 MHz; CDCl_3) δ 3.20–3.60 (3H, m, O-CH and O-CH_2), 1.10–2.20 (28H, m), 0.90 (2H, distorted t, terminal CH_3); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (22.5 MHz; CDCl_3) δ 7.75 (d, O-CH), 68.1 (t, O- CH_2), 33.3 (t), 32.5 (2C, t), 32.0 (t), 30.3 (t), 29.7 (2C, t), 29.5 (t), 26.3 (t), 25.9 (t), 24.4 (2C, t), 23.0 (t), 22.8 (t), 14.1 (q, terminal

CH_3); m/z 254 (M^+ , 16%), 211 (10), 183 (17), 154 (15), 100 (35), 83 (100), HRMS m/z for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}$, Calcd. : 254.2610. Found : 254.2636.

1-Phenylethyl methyl ether (6c) : Reductive cleavage of the dimethyl ketal **4c** (83 mg, 0.5 mmol) with NaCNBH_3 (60 mg, 0.95 mmol) and $^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ (0.02 ml, 0.074 mmol) for 4 h furnished the ether **6c** (65 mg, 93%) as an oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 1115, 1095, 760, 700 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (90 MHz; CDCl_3) δ 7.32 (5H, s, ArH), 4.27 (1H, q, J 6.2 Hz, O-CH), 3.21 (3H, s, O- CH_3), 1.42 (3H, d, J 6.2 Hz, *sec*- CH_3).

1-(4-Methylphenyl)ethyl methyl ether (6d) : Reductive cleavage of the dimethyl ketal **4d** (200 mg, 1.1 mmol) with NaCNBH_3 (120 mg, 1.9 mmol) and $^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ (0.04 ml, 0.15 mmol) for 2.5 h furnished the ether **6d** (98 mg, 59%) as an oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 1105, 1080, 810 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (90 MHz; CDCl_3) δ 7.2 (4H, s, ArH), 4.28 (1H, q, J 6.4 Hz, O-CH), 3.24 (3H, s, O- CH_3), 2.38 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3), 1.46 (3H, d, J 6.4 Hz, *sec*- CH_3); m/z 150 (M^+ , 10%), 149 (100), 135 (61), 119 (38), 91 (40).

1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)ethyl methyl ether (6e) : Reductive cleavage of the dimethyl ketal **4e** (98 mg, 0.5 mmol) with NaCNBH_3 (60 mg, 0.95 mmol) and $^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ (0.02 ml, 0.074 mmol) for 6 h furnished the ether **6e** (42 mg, 51%) as an oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 1600, 1510, 1245, 1170, 1105, 1080, 1035, 835 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (90 MHz; CDCl_3) δ 6.90 and 7.24 (4H, AB q, J 9.0 Hz, ArH), 4.26 (1H, q, J 6.4 Hz, O-CH), 3.84 (3H, s, Ar-O- CH_3), 3.20 (3H, s, O- CH_3), 1.46 (3H, d, J 6.4 Hz, *sec*- CH_3); m/z 166 (M^+ , 10%), 151 (100), 135 (52), 91 (32), HRMS m/z for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$, Calcd. : 166.0994. Found : 166.0977.

1-(4-Chlorophenyl)ethyl methyl ether (6f) : Reductive cleavage of the dimethyl ketal **4f** (150 mg, 0.75 mmol) with NaCNBH_3 (90 mg, 1.43 mmol) and $^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ (0.08 ml, 0.3 mmol) for 11 h furnished the ether **6f** (52 mg, 71%) as an oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 1120, 1085, 1010, 820 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (90 MHz; CDCl_3) δ 7.30 (4H, close AB q, J 9.0 Hz, ArH), 4.30 (1H, q, J 6.4 Hz, O-CH), 3.26 (3H, s, O- CH_3), 1.46 (3H, d, J 6.4 Hz, *sec*- CH_3); m/z 170 (M^+ , 7%) and 172 ($\text{M}^+ + 2$, 2.5), 169 (50) and 171 (18), 157 (20) and 155 (62), 141 (32) and 139 (100), 113 (15) and 111 (45).

1-(4-Bromophenyl)ethyl methyl ether (6g) : The reductive cleavage of the dimethyl ketal **4g** (122 mg, 0.5 mmol) with NaCNBH_3 (90 mg, 1.43 mmol) and $^n\text{Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ (0.08 ml, 0.3 mmol) for 11 h furnished the ether **6g** (52 mg, 49%) as an oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 1480, 1365, 1115, 1090, 1010, 825 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (90 MHz; CDCl_3) δ 7.52 and 7.20 (4H, AB q, J 9.0 Hz, ArH), 4.28 (1H, q, J 6.4 Hz, O-CH), 3.26 (3H, s, O- CH_3), 1.44 (3H, d, J 6.4 Hz, *sec*- CH_3); m/z 216 ($\text{M}^+ + 2$, 10%), 214 (M^+ , 10), 201 and 199 (100), 185 and

183 (18), 104 (25), HRMS *m/z* for C₉H₁₁BrO, Calcd. : 214.0002. Found : 213.9998.

1-Phenylethyl ethyl ether (6h) : The reductive cleavage of the mixed ketal **4h** (63 mg, 0.35 mmol) with NaCNBH₃ (60 mg, 0.95 mmol) and ⁿBu₃SnCl (0.02 ml, 0.074 mmol) for 10 h furnished the ethyl ether **6h** (40 mg, 76%) containing a small amount of the methyl ether **6c** (≈5%) : *v*_{max} (neat) 1490, 1365, 1265, 1205, 1100, 760, 695 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (80 MHz; CDCl₃) δ 7.32 (5H, s, ArH), 4.36 (1H, q, *J* 6.2 Hz, O-CH), 3.35 (2H, q, *J* 6.8 Hz, O-CH₂), 1.44 (3H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, *sec*-CH₃), 1.17 (3H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz, O-CH₂CH₃).

n-Dodecyl isopropyl ether (6i) : Reductive cleavage of the mixed ketal **4i** (130 mg, 0.5 mmol) with NaCNBH₃ (60 mg, 0.95 mmol) and ⁿBu₃SnCl (0.03 ml, 0.11 mmol) for 11 h furnished the ether **6i** (87 mg, 76%) as an oil : *v*_{max} (neat) 1370, 1360, 1140, 1125, 1080 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (90 MHz; CDCl₃) δ 3.48 (1H, septet, *J* 6.4 Hz, O-CH), 3.40 (2H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz, O-CH₂), 1.28 (20H, br s), 1.18 (6H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz, CH₃-C-CH₃), 0.88 (3H, distorted t, terminal CH₃); ¹³C NMR (67.5 MHz; CDCl₃) δ 70.2 (O-CH), 67.2 (O-CH₂), 30.9, 29.2 (2C), 28.6 (3C), 28.3 (2C), 25.2, 21.6, 21.1 (2C, CH₃-CH-CH₃), 13.0 (terminal-CH₃); *m/z* 213 (M-CH₃, 10%), 169 (12), 85 (25), 43 (100), HRMS *m/z* for C₁₄H₂₉O (M-CH₃), Calcd. : 213.2219. Found : 213.2243.

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